

COORDINATION COMPOUND OF VO (II) WITH GLUTARIC ACID AND NICOTINAMIDE

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Relevance: To maintain the stability of the internal environment of living organisms, it is extremely important to maintain physiological levels of trace elements. This fact can be explained by the fact that some trace elements are contained in the body in the form of complex coordination compounds with organic ligands, which are more biologically active and less toxic than compounds of inorganic origin. Vanadium is present in the body in very small amounts, but it is known to be involved in the regulation of carbohydrate and lipid metabolism, promotes better oxygenation of haemoglobin, has an insulin-like effect, namely, it promotes the absorption of glucose by cells, and is thought to have an antitumour effect. Nicotinamide participates in redox reactions, plays a role in blood formation, and exhibits antioxidant properties. Glutaric acid participates in energy metabolism and increases the intensity of enzymatic processes.

Research objective: synthesis and study of the physicochemical properties of VO(II) coordination compounds with ligands – glutaric acid (GLA) and nicotinamide (ANK).

Materials and methods: vanadyl sulphate, sodium hydroxide, glutaric acid and nicotinamide were used to perform this synthesis and study. The individuality of the complex was studied using an XRD-6100 diffractometer. Thermal analysis of the complex was performed on a NETZSCH STA-409 PG thermoanalyser in the temperature range of 400 °C. Quantitative determination of the metal was performed in an AA-7000 atomic absorption spectrophotometer (Shimadzu, Japan). Nitrogen was determined using the Dumas micro method. IR spectra were recorded on a Cary 630 IR Fourier spectrophotometer in the range of 400-4000 cm⁻¹ (Ftir Agilent Technologies, USA) complete with a MIRacle-10 attenuated total internal reflection (ATIR) attachment with a diamond/ZnSe prism (spectral range on the wave number scale - 4000÷400 cm⁻¹; resolution - 4 cm⁻¹, signal-to-noise ratio sensitivity - 60,000:1; scanning speed - 20 spectra per second).

The synthesis of the complex compound VO(GLK-2H)(ANK)₂ was carried out as follows: 0.004 moles of glutaric acid were dissolved in 5 ml of an aqueous solution containing 0.008 moles of caustic soda. To this, 0.004 moles of a molar solution of a metal nitrate salt were added. The resulting transparent solution was added to 50 ml of an ethanol solution containing 0.008 moles of nicotinamide while stirring. The mixture was stirred on a magnetic stirrer for 2 days. The precipitate was separated and washed with ether.

Results: The individuality of the obtained coordination compound was studied. The composition of the isolated compound was determined by elemental analysis, and some physicochemical properties were studied. The microstructure of the complexes was also investigated, and the elemental composition corresponds to the results of the atomic adsorption method. In order to establish the structure of the synthesised complex compound, IR spectroscopic and derivatographic studies were carried out.

Conclusions: A new mixed-ligand coordination compound with the composition VO(GLK-2H)(ANK)₂ has been synthesised. It was established that in the complex, deprotonated glutaric acid

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exhibits tetradentate coordination to the metal via the oxygen atoms of the carboxyl group, while nicotinamide exhibits monodentate coordination via the carbonyl oxygen atom.